

Terahertz assisted Atom Probe Tomography: Effect of THz properties on ion's behavior

Michella Karam^{1*}, Loïc Rousseau¹, Ganesh Damarla¹, Jonathan Houard¹ and Angela Vella¹

¹. Normandie Université, UNIROUEN, INSA Rouen, CNRS, Groupe de Physique des Matériaux, 76000, Rouen, France

* Michella Karam michella.karam@univ-rouen.fr

The atom probe tomography (APT) provides three-dimensional compositional mapping on an atomic scale. It allows to identify the chemical nature of the elements present in the material thanks to Time-Of-Flight Mass Spectrometry [TOF-MS] [1]. Its principle is based on the extraction of surface atoms from a nanometric needle-shaped sample biased at a high DC field. The DC electric field combined with a voltage pulse or a focused laser pulse triggers the extraction of the atoms, one by one, from the surface in a well-controlled way. The voltage pulses are used for metallic sample analysis while the laser pulses are used for non-metallic samples. However, the interaction of these pulses with the material induce a thermal heating which causes a low spatial and chemical resolutions [1].

We recently proposed to use a monocycle THz pulse in order to perform a high-resolution imaging. In this case, the electric field will increase by several GV/m at the apex of the sample during a fraction of the THz monocycle [2,3]. Therefore, a non-thermal emission of the surface atoms in the form of ions is triggered .

Here we study the effect of the THz monocycle parameters on the TOF-MS. We present numerical simulations of ion trajectories, for different ion masses. We calculate their time of flight as a function of different durations, shapes and amplitudes of THz pulse (Fig 1(a-b)). We prove that the energy acquired by the emitted ions depends on these parameters, and consequently affects the shape of their time of flight spectra as shown in Fig 1 (c).

Fig. 1 (a) The three THz pulses we used, having the same shape and duration but different amplitudes: 1.5 kV (Red), 3 kV (Blue) and 4.5 kV (Black). The grey block indicates the zone with the higher probability of extraction. (b) Variation in time of flight behaviour of B^{1+} , removed from the tip apex under the action of the pulses, during the selected time shown in (Fig 1(a), grey block). (c) B^{1+} ToF spectrums obtained by numerical results at different amplitudes of THz (1.5 kV (Red), 3 kV (Blue) and 4.5 kV (Black)). Then we present the comparison of those numerical spectrums with an experimental one (grey) we got from analyzing a LaB6 sample.

We compare our numerical results to the experimental ones we got during the analysis of a LaB6 sample,(Fig1(c)). Therefore, we provide the ideal parameters for the THz monocycle to get the highest imaging resolution.

References

- [1] Lefebvre W, Vurpillot F, Sauvage X, editors. Atom probe tomography: put theory into practice. Academic Press; 2016 May 30.
- [2] Houard, J., Normand, A., Di Russo, E., Bacchi, C., Dalapati, P., Beainy, G., ... & Rigutti, L. (2020). *A photonic atom probe coupling 3D atomic scale analysis with in situ photoluminescence spectroscopy*. Review of Scientific Instruments, *91*(8), 083704
- [3]VELLA, Angela, HOUARD, Jonathan, ARNOLDI, Laurent, et al. High-resolution terahertzdriven atom probe tomography. Science Advances, 2021, vol. 7, no 7, p. eabd7259.